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OPEN BOOK VECTOR CALCULUS ASSESSMENT: SUGGESTED DESIGN PRINCIPLES

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ABSTRACT

Traditionally mathematics tests are done with paper and pencil, no calculator and are written in a secure venue. In March 2020, with three weeks' notice, we had to change our plans to administer a traditional vector calculus test and instead run assessment that was open book and written remotely, with access to electronic tools. The biggest surprise was how easy this was to do. Much of multivariable calculus and vector calculus is dependent on understanding what the question is asking, visualising curves and surfaces and how they interact with one another, and setting up sometimes quite complicated integrals. The final few steps of actually computing the integral are the least important part of any problem. In this short paper I shall set out and motivate design principles for setting such a test, based on our experience in March 2020 and more recently refined in March 2021.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Calculus courses at university are traditionally assessed with closed book tests. Courses adopting a continuous assessment model might include homework assignments, projects, quizzes and so forth but a final summative closed book test remains a mainstay of calculus assessment. In March 2020 at our institution, as at so many others, we were forced by circumstances to shift to online testing. With very little time to prepare the simplest model was non-proctored open book tests which necessarily meant open internet tests. The students would have access to their notes, their textbook, computer graphing packages and online calculators. Hereafter in this article “open book” will refer to “open book and open internet”.

Somewhat hastily we developed principles to guide the setting of the test. In 2021 with more time to prepare and the opportunity to reflect on the 2020 experience these principles were made more explicit and are discussed in this article. As observed by Kahn [1] entry level calculus courses are arguably a poor fit for open book testing, but higher level courses in which we assess for “higher level understanding, such as the ability to reason, conceptualize and solve problems, and not simply memory and knowledge” (p. 1070) are a far better fit. Trenholm [2] observes that in a survey of fully asynchronous online mathematics courses developmental mathematics courses tended significantly more towards proctored assessment than calculus courses preferring closed book tests. While in this article the term open book is being explicitly used to mean access to all notes as well as online resources, the term open book is used variably. Raen [3] uses “open book” to mean access to a self-created formula sheet while Edwards and Loch [4] differentiate between closed book, access to formula sheet, and fully open book.

2 METHODOLOGY

The first step in the design of this test was to go through the syllabus and a selection of previous test papers and make a list of all the types of questions that were typical to ask. Secondly, obvious poor candidates for open book testing were identified. Third, certain types of questions were tested against popular online calculators.

A set of design principles was derived, mostly implicitly at the time given the urgency, but made more explicit in post hoc reflection. The test and the resit (a second chance at the test) were set according to these design principles. In 2021 we were able to refine and be explicit about our design principles.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Observations leading to design principles

Steps one and two of the process involved detailed listing of all types of test questions we could ask and to identify obvious poor candidates for an open book test. These included solving integrals already provided in symbolic form, and calculating div and curl of vector fields. The third step of the process was to test how well popular online calculators could be used. It was determined that typical “change the order of integration” questions were easily solved by online calculators if the

integral was provided in the non-solvable order. The first four of the five design principles listed below were used to draw up the test and resit in 2020.

In 2021 the four design principles were formulated more explicitly after their hurried framing in 2020 and were used to design the first test. Reflection on that test and looking back at the 2020 experience suggested the addition of the fifth design principle below. In short the design principles are (1) Provide diagrams, (2) Encourage decision making, (3) Create opportunities for noticing options, (4) Low emphasis on solving integrals, and (5) Avoid formats that have characteristic forms.

3.2 Design principles

Provide diagrams – Two reasons support inclusion of diagrams, those are equity and information interpretation. In a closed book test it can be reasonable to require students to draw a diagram as part of their solution. This requirement is no longer reasonable when the student has access to computer graphing packages and could be regarded as inequitable if some students were more practised at using such packages. Furthermore, providing information through diagrams rather than text requires translating the information into a form useful for the problem's requirements.

Encourage decision making – Provide information-rich problems requiring decisions over what exactly is required; information is given in one form and needs to be changed into another form. Students have to decide what is important and why.

Create opportunities for noticing options – The nature of the vector calculus context is that often there are multiple ways of solving problems. Examples include solving line integrals of conservative vector fields, and replacing a surface in a Stokes' Theorem problem.

Low emphasis on solving integrals – Since online calculators can solve most integrals once limits of integration have been determined there is little point in assessing this skill in an open book context. Put emphasis on the set up of integrals and low emphasis on solving or omit solving altogether.

Avoid formats that have characteristic forms – Avoid situations where a familiar form, for example the line integral of a Green's Theorem problem, triggers the means to solve the problem rather than any decision making on the students' part.

3.3 Example 1 – line integral of (conservative) vector field

The question below is underpinned by design principles 2 and 3, that of encouraging decision making and providing options. Answering part (a) could be done by finding a potential function or by calculating curl. Answering (b) can be done using a line integral for the entirety of \mathbf{G} or by employing a potential function for the \mathbf{F} part of \mathbf{G} and the line integral only for the second part of \mathbf{G} .

Let $\mathbf{F}(x, y, z) = \langle yz + ze^{xz}, xz + z \cos yz, A \rangle$ and let $\mathbf{G}(x, y, z) = \mathbf{F}(x, y, z) + \langle y, -x, 0 \rangle$.

- What must A be equal to in order for \mathbf{F} to be a conservative vector field? Choose the simplest option.
- Let A be whatever you determined in (a). Determine the work done by \mathbf{G} to move a particle along the line segment from $(1, 2, 0)$ to $(0, 3, 1)$.

3.4 Example 2 – describing a region

The equation of the circle is not given, the student needs to combine the information given in text and in the diagram. This question illustrates design principle 1.

The region in the diagram is bounded by a circle of radius 1. Describe that region in (a) Polar coordinates and (b) Rectangular coordinates.

Fig. 1 diagram for Example 2

3.5 Example 3 – Green's Theorem for area

This question is underpinned by design principles 2 and 4, that of decision making and low emphasis on solving of integrals. Once the integral is correctly set up it proves to be easy to solve.

A particle moves along the curve $\mathbf{r}(t) = \langle t^2 - 2t, t^3 - 4t \rangle, t \in \mathbb{R}$ which bounds the shaded region shown in the diagram. Evaluate the area of that bounded region.

Figure 2. Diagram for Example 3

4 SUMMARY

The sudden requirement to set open book tests in April 2020 required hasty development of design principles which were later refined in 2021. In this paper we have used “open book” to refer to “open book and internet” and hence access to online calculators. A complication in 2020 and 2021 which we hope will have been resolved by 2022 is that the remote, non-proctored nature of the tests could still lead to cheating such as communication with others, both in person and online.

In 2022 we hope to allow students to bring in notes and to have access to certain online resources, such as computer graphing packages and online calculators, while constraining the environment to avoid the potential for cheating unavoidable in 2020 and 2021. We look forward to this new mode of vector calculus testing, thrust upon us initially unwillingly, but upon reflection improving our assessment.

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